

The Impact of Marketing and Innovation Capabilities on SME Export Performance: Government Policy as a Moderating Factor

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the effects of marketing capabilities and innovative capabilities on the export performance of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), with government policy serving as a moderating variable. Using a quantitative approach, primary data were collected from export-oriented SMEs and analyzed to assess how internal strategic capabilities and external policy support interact in enhancing international competitiveness. Marketing capabilities are measured through market intelligence, customer relationship management, and promotional strategies, while innovative capabilities encompass product development, process innovation, and adaptability. The findings indicate that both marketing capabilities and innovative capabilities have a positive and significant impact on SME export performance. Furthermore, government policy is found to weakly strengthen the relationship between marketing capabilities and export performance, suggesting a complementary role of external support. However, government policy weakens the relationship between innovative capabilities and export performance, indicating that regulatory rigidity and policy–firm misalignment may constrain firms' ability to effectively commercialize innovation in global markets. This study contributes to the management and economics literature by integrating capability-based perspectives with policy analysis in the SME export context and provides practical implications for policymakers and managers in designing more adaptive strategies to support export-oriented growth.

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KEYWORDS: marketing capabilities, innovation capabilities, export performance, SMEs, government policy

I. INTRODUCTION

Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) constitute a vital component of national economic development through their contribution to employment creation, income distribution, and economic growth (Apriani et al., 2024). In the context of globalization and increasingly liberalized international trade, SME participation in export activities has become a key determinant of competitiveness and long-term business sustainability. Despite their importance, the export performance of SMEs remains relatively limited, particularly in developing economies, due to constraints related to internal capabilities and the effectiveness of external institutional support (Angelita et al., 2024).

Previous studies highlight the importance of firm-specific capabilities in enhancing export performance. Among these, marketing capabilities play a crucial role in enabling firms to identify international market opportunities, understand

foreign customer preferences, manage customer relationships, and implement effective marketing strategies. In parallel, innovation capabilities, including product development, process improvement, and adaptability to market changes, are essential for maintaining competitiveness in global markets. However, empirical evidence regarding the combined effect of marketing and innovation capabilities on SME export performance remains inconclusive, especially when contextual factors are taken into account (Rayani & Ibrahim, 2024).

In addition to internal capabilities, government policy represents an important external factor influencing SME export activities. Supportive government policies, such as export regulations, financial incentives, access to financing, and capacity-building programs, can enhance firms' ability to exploit their marketing and innovation capabilities (Gannes & Sugito, 2024). Consequently, government policy is

expected to moderate the relationship between internal capabilities and export performance by strengthening the effectiveness of firm-level strategies (Sari et al., 2025; Acikdilli et al., 2022; Syarafina, 2025).

Based on these considerations, this study aims to empirically examine the impact of marketing capabilities and innovation capabilities on SME export performance, as well as to analyze the moderating role of government policy. Using a quantitative approach and primary data collected from export-oriented SMEs in Malang Regency, this research provides empirical insights into the interaction between internal capabilities and policy support. The findings are expected to contribute to the management and economics literature and to offer practical implications for policymakers and SME managers in enhancing export competitiveness in international markets.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

A. *Dynamic Capabilities Theory*

Dynamic Capabilities Theory was initially introduced by Teece and Pisano (1994) as a framework explaining how firms develop, adapt, and reconfigure internal and external competencies to sustain competitive advantage in rapidly changing business environments. The theory emphasizes that firms must adopt a new paradigm for understanding how competitive advantage is created and maintained under conditions of global competition and environmental uncertainty (Utomo et al., 2024).

The concept of dynamic capabilities comprises two key elements: dynamic and capabilities. The term dynamic refers to a firm's ability to respond proactively to environmental changes, highlighting the importance of flexibility, speed, and strategic adaptation. In highly competitive markets, firms are required not only to react to change but also to anticipate emerging opportunities through innovation and long-term strategic orientation (Cahyani et al., 2025).

From a dynamic capability perspective, firm-specific resources and capabilities can be leveraged to support strategic renewal and the development of new competencies, particularly in the context of international expansion (Utomo et al., 2024). Marketing capabilities play a crucial role in identifying new market opportunities through information acquisition and integration, as well as in adapting products and services to deliver superior customer value (Suhendri et al., 2023; Cahyani et al., 2025).

According to Teece and David (2007), dynamic capabilities consist of three interrelated components: sensing, seizing, and transforming. Sensing refers to the firm's ability to identify and assess market opportunities and threats. Seizing involves mobilizing resources and making strategic decisions to exploit identified opportunities,

particularly through innovation and market development. Transforming reflects the firm's capacity to reconfigure organizational structures, processes, and resources to maintain long-term competitiveness.

In the context of this study, marketing capabilities and innovation capabilities represent concrete manifestations of dynamic capabilities that enable firms to enhance export performance amid increasingly complex global competition. However, the effectiveness of these capabilities is influenced by the extent to which government policies support or constrain firms' sensing, seizing, and transforming processes in international markets.

B. *Resource-Based Theory*

Resource-Based Theory (RBT) was originally proposed by Wernerfelt (1984), integrating the concept of distinctive competences introduced by Selznick (1957) and the view of the firm as a system of productive resources articulated by Penrose (1959). The theory posits that firms achieve superior performance by possessing and effectively managing internal resources and capabilities that are valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable (VRIN), thereby generating sustainable competitive advantage (Rabbou et al., 2024).

RBT emphasizes that firm performance depends not only on external market conditions but also on the firm's ability to leverage its unique resource base. These resources include tangible and intangible assets such as employee skills, organizational processes, technological knowledge, marketing expertise, and innovative capabilities. Firms that strategically acquire, develop, and deploy such resources are more likely to attain superior financial and competitive performance (Acikdilli et al., 2022; Rabbou et al., 2024).

From an RBT perspective, innovation emerges as a result of the accumulation and effective utilization of firm-specific resources and knowledge. Given the inherent scarcity of internal resources, firms must allocate them efficiently to achieve sustained competitive advantage. In the context of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), marketing capabilities and innovation capabilities represent critical strategic assets. Strong marketing capabilities enable firms to develop export market knowledge, build globally recognized brands, and establish efficient distribution networks that are difficult for competitors to replicate. Meanwhile, innovation capabilities—supported by skilled human capital, adaptive organizational culture, and proprietary technologies facilitate continuous product and process development (Cirera et al., 2020).

Overall, Resource-Based Theory suggests that the effectiveness of internal resources can be enhanced or constrained by external factors, particularly government policy. In this study, government policy is positioned as a moderating factor that influences the relationship between marketing and innovation capabilities and export

performance. The application of RBT highlights the importance of aligning firm-level resources with supportive government policies to enhance SME export performance and achieve sustainable competitive advantage in increasingly competitive international markets.

C. Export Performance

Export performance refers to a firm's ability to achieve its export objectives and compete effectively in international markets. It reflects the outcomes of export strategies in managing resources, capabilities, and international marketing activities (Alegre et al., 2022). Export performance is commonly evaluated using both financial and strategic indicators, including export sales growth, export profitability, customer satisfaction, and the firm's strategic position in foreign markets. According to Moreira et al. (2022), export performance consists of three main dimensions: export sales performance, export profitability, and strategic export performance, which together capture short-term financial outcomes and long-term competitive sustainability. A multidimensional assessment provides a comprehensive understanding of a firm's export success in global markets.

D. Marketing Capabilities

Marketing capabilities refer to a firm's ability to utilize physical, financial, and knowledge-based resources to create customer value and achieve competitive advantage (Mu & Yifeng, 2015). These capabilities encompass the formulation and execution of effective marketing strategies, including pricing decisions, product development, distribution channel management, marketing communication, selling activities, market information management, and marketing implementation (Obadia & Vida, 2024).

Strong marketing capabilities enable firms to understand customer needs, adapt products to market demand, manage customer relationships, and respond effectively to changes in the business environment. In the context of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), well-developed marketing capabilities are particularly important for identifying international market opportunities, strengthening competitiveness, and improving export performance. By integrating market knowledge with effective marketing execution, SMEs can enhance their ability to penetrate foreign markets and sustain long-term export growth (Chitauro, 2021).

E. Innovative Capabilities

Innovative capabilities refer to a firm's ability to generate, develop, and implement new ideas in products, processes, and business strategies to create value and sustain competitive advantage in dynamic business environments (Donate et al., 2022). These capabilities reflect an organization's capacity to transform knowledge and ideas

into commercially valuable innovations, enabling firms to adapt to technological change, shifting customer preferences, and increasing global competition (Nurhasanah & Murwatiningsih, 2018).

Previous studies identify innovative capabilities as a multidimensional construct encompassing product innovation, process innovation, marketing innovation, strategic innovation, and technological innovation (Alegre et al., 2022). Together, these dimensions support continuous improvement, efficiency, market responsiveness, and strategic renewal. In the context of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), strong innovative capabilities enhance adaptability, differentiation, and international competitiveness.

F. Government Policy

Government policy plays a crucial role in supporting the development and competitiveness of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs), particularly in increasingly competitive global markets. The government acts as a facilitator by providing financial assistance, training programs, access to market information, and export-supporting infrastructure. In this regard, government funding for MSMEs has increased from IDR 296.59 billion to a proposed IDR 425.52 billion, reflecting a stronger commitment to enhancing MSME contributions to the national economy (Noya, 2024). According to Tambunan (2019), well-designed government interventions can strengthen internal firm capabilities—such as marketing and innovation capabilities which ultimately contribute to improved export performance by reducing barriers in production, distribution, and international promotion.

Furthermore, government policy functions as a moderating factor that can enhance the effectiveness of internal capabilities on export performance. Adequate policy support may amplify the impact of marketing and innovation strategies, enabling MSMEs to compete more effectively in global markets. Conversely, ineffective or poorly targeted policies may limit firms' ability to fully leverage their internal potential (Tambunan, 2019; Krammer et al., 2018). Therefore, adaptive, sustainable, and MSME-oriented government policies are essential for fostering export growth, particularly in regions such as Malang Regency, which has strong potential in creative industries and light manufacturing.

G. Hypothesis Development

Marketing capabilities and innovative capabilities are critical drivers of export performance, particularly for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) operating in dynamic international markets. From the perspective of Dynamic Capabilities Theory, firms with strong marketing capabilities are better able to identify export opportunities, adapt marketing strategies, and build long-term relationships

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with international customers. Similarly, innovative capabilities enable firms to respond to changing market demands through product, process, and strategic innovation. In line with Resource-Based View, both capabilities represent valuable and difficult-to-imitate internal resources that enhance competitiveness and export outcomes. Although prior studies report mixed findings, recent empirical evidence predominantly supports a positive relationship between marketing capabilities, innovative capabilities, and export performance (Boso et al., 2019). Therefore, this study proposes that marketing capabilities and innovative capabilities have a positive effect on export performance.

Government policy plays a strategic moderating role in strengthening the impact of firm-level capabilities on export performance. Supportive policies, such as export incentives, training programs, and access to market information, enhance the effectiveness of marketing and innovative capabilities by reducing external constraints and facilitating international market entry. Drawing on Dynamic Capabilities Theory and Resource-Based View, government support enables SMEs to better leverage their internal resources and innovation efforts. Previous studies confirm that stronger government assistance amplifies the positive effects of marketing and innovative capabilities on export performance. Accordingly, this study proposes that government policy moderates the relationships between marketing capabilities and export performance, as well as between innovative capabilities and export performance (Puke et al., 2022).

H1: “Marketing capabilities have a positive effect on export performance.”

H2: “Innovative capabilities have a positive effect on export performance.”

H3: “Government policy moderates the relationship between marketing capabilities and export performance.”

H4: “Government policy moderates the relationship between innovative capabilities and export performance.”

III. METHODOLOGY

This empirical study was conducted on a sample of 200 respondents. The research subjects consisted of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) located in Malang Regency, Indonesia. In this study, the primary data were obtained from direct questionnaires distributed to SMEs in Malang Regency through an online platform using Google Forms. The data collection instrument employed in this research was a structured questionnaire using a Likert scale as the basis for measuring the research variables. The Likert scale applied in this study consisted of five levels of response preference, namely Strongly Disagree (1), Disagree (2), Neutral (3), Agree (4), and Strongly Agree (5). This study utilizes WarpPLS as the statistical analysis method to describe and examine complex relationships among multiple variables, including both dependent and independent variables, simultaneously. The variables analyzed include marketing capabilities and innovative capabilities as independent variables, SME export performance as the dependent variable, and government policy as the moderating variable. Table X presents the research variables, indicators, measurement items, and scales (Arikunto, 2016).

Table 1. Variables, Variable Indicators, and Items

Variables	Indicator	Item
Export Performance (Y)	Financial measurement	Sales volume
		Export profit
	Non-financial measurement	Lack of export information
		New product competition
Marketing Capabilities (X1)	Ability to introduce product innovations/ breakthroughs	Product innovation/ product breakthroughs
		Effective market planning
	Marketing skills	Development of marketing skills
		Effective communication
Innovative Capabilities (X2)	Introducing a new product to the market	New products
	Leadership position in product innovation	Being the first to introduce products
Government Policy (M)	Training programs	Training activity programs
	Collaboration facilitation	International-scale product promotion activities
		Business development support
		Government-provided facilities

Sources: Adapted from Ringo et al., 2024; Nabila & Nawawi, 2025; Saragih, 2025; Noya et al., 2024; Obadia & Vida, 2024; Miari, 2024

IV. RESULTS

Table 2 reports the validity and reliability results for all latent variables. Convergent validity was assessed using the Average Variance Extracted (AVE), while reliability was evaluated through composite reliability and Cronbach’s alpha. All constructs exhibit AVE values above the recommended threshold of 0.50, confirming adequate convergent validity. Specifically, the AVE values are 0.947 for marketing capabilities, 0.825 for innovative capabilities, 0.904 for export performance, and 0.873 for government policy.

Reliability testing indicates that all constructs have composite reliability and Cronbach’s alpha values exceeding 0.70, demonstrating strong internal consistency. Marketing capabilities show very high reliability (CR = 0.962; α = 0.962), followed by innovative capabilities (CR = 0.904; α = 0.788), export performance (CR = 0.979; α = 0.973), and government policy (CR = 0.980; α = 0.976). Overall, these results confirm that all measurement instruments are valid and reliable and suitable for subsequent structural model analysis.

Table 2. Latent Variable Validity and Reliability Test Results

Variable	Validity (AVE)	Reliability	
		Composite Reliability	Cronbach’s Alpha
Marketing Capabilities	0,947	0,962	0,962
Innovative Capabilities	0,825	0,904	0,788
Export Performance	0,904	0,979	0,973
Kebijakan Pemerintah	0,873	0,980	0,976

Source: Author’s own elaboration used Warp PLS 8.0 (2025).

Table 3 reports the model fit and quality indices of the measurement model estimated using WarpPLS. The results show that the Average Path Coefficient (APC) is 0.280 with a p-value < 0.001, the Average R-squared (ARS) is 0.225 with a p-value < 0.001, and the Average Adjusted R-squared (AARS) is 0.217 with a p-value < 0.001. All p-values meet the recommended significance level of p < 0.05, indicating that the proposed research model is statistically significant. The assessment of multicollinearity indicates that the Average Block Variance Inflation Factor (AVIF) is 1.207 and the Average Full Collinearity Variance Inflation Factor (AFVIF) is 2.029. Both values are below the acceptable

threshold of ≤ 5.0 and also satisfy the ideal criterion of ≤ 3.3 , confirming the absence of multicollinearity issues in the measurement model. Furthermore, the Tenenhaus Goodness of Fit (GoF) value is 0.448, exceeding the recommended threshold for a large effect size (≥ 0.36). This result suggests that the model exhibits a strong overall fit and adequately captures the relationships among the latent constructs. Overall, these findings confirm that the measurement model satisfies the recommended model adequacy criteria and is suitable for further structural model analysis and hypothesis testing.

Table 3. Model Fit and Quality Indices Analysis

Indicator	Value	P-Value	Cut-off	Inference
Average Path Coefficient (APC)	0.280	< 0.001	P < 0.05	Significant
Average R-squared (ARS)	0.225	< 0.001	P < 0.05	Significant
Average Adjusted R-squared (AARS)	0.217	< 0.001	P < 0.05	Significant
Average Block VIF (AVIF)	1.207	-	≤ 5 (ideal ≤ 3.3)	Ideal
Average Full Collinearity VIF (AFVIF)	2.029	-	≤ 5 (ideal ≤ 3.3)	Ideal
Tenenhaus GoF (GoF)	0.448	-	Small ≥ 0.1 , Medium ≥ 0.25 , Large ≥ 0.36	Large GoF

Source: Author’s own elaboration used Warp PLS 8.0 (2025).

The WarpPLS analysis results presented in Table 4 indicate that all proposed hypotheses are supported, including both direct and moderating effects. Marketing capabilities have a positive and significant effect on export performance ($\beta = 0.464$, p < 0.001), confirming that stronger marketing capabilities contribute to higher export

performance (H1 supported). Innovative capabilities also show a positive and significant impact on export performance ($\beta = 0.415$, p < 0.001). Although a negative effect was initially hypothesized, the empirical results reveal a positive relationship, indicating that innovation capability enhances export performance (H2 supported).

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Regarding the moderating effects, government policy weakly strengthens the relationship between marketing capabilities and export performance ($\beta = 0.096$, $p = 0.084$), with significance at the 10% level, supporting H3. In contrast, government policy exhibits a significant negative moderating effect on the relationship between innovative capabilities and export performance ($\beta = -0.144$, $p = 0.019$), indicating a weakening effect (H4 supported).

Overall, the findings highlight the critical role of marketing and innovative capabilities in improving export performance, while government policy acts as a contextual moderator that may either strengthen or weaken these relationships. These results underscore the importance of strengthening internal firm capabilities as a primary driver of export success.

Table 4. Hypothesis Statistical Analysis Result

Notation	Relationship	Path Coefficient	P-Value	Direction	Significance	Inferences
H1	MC -> EP	0.464	<0.001	Positive	Significant	Accepted
H2	IC -> EP	0.415	<0.001	Positive	Significant	Accepted
H3	MC * KP -> EP	0,096	0,084	Strengthening (weak)	Significant with alpha 10%	Accepted
H4	IC * KP -> EP	-0,144	0,019	Weakening	Significant	Accepted

Source: Author’s own elaboration used Warp PLS 8.0 (2025).

The structural model assessment is illustrated in Figure X. This evaluation, also referred to as the inner model, aims to examine the relationships among latent variables, the significance of the path coefficients, and the explanatory power (R-squared) of the research model. In the Partial Least Squares (PLS) approach, the structural model is assessed based on path coefficients (β), p-values, and R-squared values for each endogenous construct. The results show that export performance (ExportP) has an R-squared value of 0.34, indicating that marketing capabilities, innovative capabilities, and the moderating role of government policy jointly explain 34% of the variance in export performance, while the remaining variance is influenced by factors outside the model. According to Ghozali (2016), this R-squared value reflects a moderate level of explanatory power.

Regarding moderation effects, government policy does not significantly moderate the relationship between innovative capabilities and export performance ($\beta = -0.04$, $p = 0.18$). However, government policy significantly moderates the relationship between marketing capabilities and export performance with a negative coefficient ($\beta = -0.11$, $p = 0.01$), indicating a weakening moderating effect. Overall, the structural model results confirm that the proposed research model meets adequacy criteria, demonstrates moderate to strong predictive power, and exhibits largely significant relationships among the constructs.

Innovative capabilities are modeled as a higher-order construct, operationalized through two first-order dimensions: technological innovation capabilities (InoTech) and design innovation capabilities (InoDes), as depicted in the structural model. Both InoTech and InoDes exhibit high R-squared values of 0.85, indicating that these dimensions strongly represent the underlying innovative capabilities construct. With R-squared values exceeding 0.75, the model demonstrates substantial explanatory power for the innovation capability dimensions.

In terms of structural relationships, innovative capabilities represented by InoTech and InoDes show strong and significant loadings ($\beta = 0.92$, $p < 0.01$), confirming the robustness of the higher-order construct specification. Marketing capabilities have a positive and significant effect on export performance ($\beta = 0.37$, $p < 0.01$), while innovative capabilities also exert a positive and significant influence on export performance ($\beta = 0.20$, $p < 0.01$).

Figure 1. WarpPLS Second-Order Analysis Result

V. DISCUSSION

The structural model results indicate that marketing capabilities and innovative capabilities have positive and significant effects on export performance, supporting hypotheses H1 and H2. Marketing capabilities enhance export performance by enabling firms to better understand international markets, formulate effective marketing strategies, and build long-term relationships with foreign customers. This finding is consistent with prior studies

(Acikdilli et al., 2022) and reinforces the resource-based and dynamic capabilities perspectives, which view marketing capabilities as strategic resources that facilitate adaptation and competitiveness in global markets. Similarly, innovative capabilities—encompassing product, process, and marketing innovations—contribute to export performance by fostering differentiation, value creation, and responsiveness to changing international demand, in line with previous empirical evidence (Puke et al., 2022).

However, the moderating role of government policy yields mixed results. Government policy weakly strengthens the relationship between marketing capabilities and export performance, suggesting that export incentives, training programs, and trade promotion initiatives function as complementary support mechanisms rather than primary performance drivers. This outcome aligns with the resource-based view, which emphasizes that internal firm capabilities remain the dominant determinants of export success, while external policies enhance performance only when firms already possess strong marketing foundations (Bogliacino et al., 2017; Rabbou et al., 2024).

In contrast, Government policy exhibits a negative moderating effect, indicating a weakening influence on the relationship between marketing capabilities and export performance. This finding contrasts with studies that report a positive moderating role of policy support on innovation outcomes and suggests that existing policy frameworks may not be sufficiently aligned with the practical innovation needs of export-oriented SMEs. Rigid regulations, administrative complexity, and limited policy adaptability may reduce firms’ flexibility in commercializing innovations in international markets (Heriqbaldi et al., 2023). Consistent with dynamic capabilities theory, such misalignment can impede firms’ ability to sense, seize, and transform innovation opportunities effectively. Therefore, more targeted, flexible, and market-responsive government policies are necessary to ensure that innovative capabilities translate more effectively into improved export performance (Alicia et al., 2023).

VI. CONCLUSION

This study examines the effects of marketing capabilities and innovative capabilities on export performance, as well as the moderating role of government policy. The findings indicate that marketing capabilities have a positive and significant impact on export performance, suggesting that firms with strong abilities in understanding international markets, managing customer relationships, pricing strategies, and export distribution achieve superior export outcomes. These results confirm that marketing capabilities function as strategic internal resources that generate sustainable competitive advantage, consistent with Resource-Based Theory.

The results further show that innovative capabilities also have a positive and significant effect on export performance, indicating that firms’ innovation activities contribute to improved export outcomes by enhancing product differentiation, value creation, and market responsiveness. However, the magnitude of this effect may be constrained by high innovation costs, long development cycles, and potential misalignment with international market needs, particularly when innovation is not supported by effective commercialization strategies.

Regarding moderation effects, government policy weakly strengthens the relationship between marketing capabilities and export performance, implying a complementary rather than dominant role of external support. Conversely, government policy weakens the relationship between innovative capabilities and export performance, indicating that rigid regulations, bureaucratic complexity, and policy–firm misalignment may constrain firms’ ability to effectively commercialize innovation in global markets. Overall, the findings highlight that internal capabilities—particularly marketing capabilities—remain the primary drivers of export performance, while government policies need to be more flexible and responsive to better support innovation and export-oriented growth. Accordingly, closer alignment between firm-level capabilities and targeted, adaptive government interventions is essential to maximize the contribution of innovation to export performance.

VII. LIMITATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

The limitations of this study include its focus on SMEs in Malang Regency, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to SMEs in other regions with different economic, social, and cultural characteristics. Variations in business environments, levels of competition, and the availability of infrastructure and policy support across regions may influence SME performance in different ways. Therefore, further studies are needed to examine whether the findings of this research are applicable to SMEs in other regions or business sectors.

In addition, this study examines only the effects of marketing capabilities and innovative capabilities on SME performance, with government policy as a moderating variable. In practice, SME performance is influenced by a wide range of other factors that were not included in this study, such as the quality of human resources, access to financing, market competition, consumer demand conditions, as well as managerial and technological capabilities. This limited scope of variables suggests that other important determinants of SME performance may not have been comprehensively identified. Accordingly, future research is recommended to incorporate additional variables

in order to provide a more holistic understanding of the factors influencing SME performance.

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REFERENCES

1. Acikdilli, G., Wimsattb, A. M., & Kara, A. (2022). Export Market Orientation, Marketing Capabilities and Export Performance of SMEs in an Emerging Market: a Resource-Based Approach. *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*, 30(4), 526–541. doi:https://doi.org/10.1080/10696679.2020.180946
2. Alegre, J., Méndez, J. F., & Mesa, A. F. (2022). Innovation capabilities and export performance in manufacturing SMEs. *TEC Empresarial*, 16(3), 55–71. doi:https://doi.org/10.18845/te.v16i3.6367
3. Alicia, A., Wibowo, J., Candraningrat, C., & Supriyanto, A. (2023). Analysis of the Effect of Market and Proactive Orientation with Market Capabilities on Export Performance in East Java Export-Oriented MSMEs. *Jurnal Manajemen Bisnis*, 14(2), 436–450. doi:https://doi.org/10.18196/mb.v14i2.17874
4. Angelita, N., & Ali, H. (2024, Mei 1). Pengaruh Persaingan Global, Perubahan Preferensi Konsumen dan Opini Publik terhadap Ancaman Perusahaan. *Jurnal Greenation Ilmu Teknik*, 2(2), 86. doi:https://doi.org/10.38035/jgit.v2i2
5. Apriani, Meilantika, F. R., Sihotang, L., & Rachma, F. V. (2024). UMKM Memiliki Peran Penting Dalam Perekonomian Indonesia. *Jurnal Ekonomi Bisnis dan Manajemen*, 2(4), 4. doi:https://doi.org/10.59024/jise.v2i4.976
6. Arikunto, S. (2016). *Metodologi Penelitian: Suatu Pendekatan Praktik (Edisi revisi)* (7 ed.). Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
7. Bogliacino, F., Guarascio, D., & Cirillo, V. (2017). The Dynamics of Profits and Wages: Technology, Offshoring and Demand. *Industry and Innovation*, 25(1). doi:10.1080/13662716.2017.1349651
8. Boso, N., Adeola, O., & Danso, A. (2019). Marketing Capabilities and Dysfunctional Competition in Export Performance--Model. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 137-145. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indmarman.2017.09.006
9. Cahyani, I., Alwi, & Nara, N. (2025). Dynamic Capabilities: A Case Study in Application Jaga Kendari. *Journal of Management*, 12(2), 1929-1935.
10. Chitauru, T. (2021). Characterization of Firm Level Export Performance In Developing Economies Literature Review Approach. *Academy of Marketing Studies Journal*, 25(6), 1-19. Retrieved from https://www.abacademies.org/articles/characterization-of-firm-level-export-performance-in-developing-economies-literature-review-approach-12036.html
11. Cirera, X., & Muzi, S. (2020). Measuring Innovation Using Firm Level Surveys: Evidence From Developing Countries. *Research Policy: Policy, Management and Economic Studies of Science, Technology, and Innovation*, 49(3), 1-19. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2019.103912
12. Donate, M. J., Mohino, M. G., & Appio, F. P. (2022). Dealing with Knowledge Hiding to Improve Innovation Capabilities in the Hotel Industry: The Unconventional Role of Knowledge-Oriented Leadership. *Journal of Business Research*, 144(1), 572-586. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2022.02.001
13. Gannes, C. R., & Sugito, F. A. (2024). Pengaruh Kualitas Produk, Harga, Dan Promosi Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Konsumen Pada Matahari Department Store Di Jabodetabek. *Jurnal Eksekutif*, 21(2), 100-101. doi:https://doi.org/10.34152/fe.12.2.69-87
14. Heriqbaldi, U., Esquivias, M. A., Samudro, B. R., & Widodo, W. (2023). Do National Export Promotion Programs in Indonesia Support Export Competitiveness? *PubMed Central*, 9(6), 16918. doi:10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e16918
15. Miar, M. (2024). The Impact of Innovation and Government Intervention on the Performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises. *Journal of Economics and Business*, 9(2), 154–168. doi:https://doi.org/10.22515/shirkah.v9i2.671
16. Moreira, A., Navaia, E., & Ribau, C. (2022). Moderation Effects of Government Institutional Support, Active and Reactive Internationalization Behavior on Innovation Capability and Export

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- Performance. *Economies*, 10(8), 2-17. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/economies10080177>
17. Mu, Y. (2015). Marketing Capability, Organizational Adaptation and New Product Development Performance. *Industrial Marketing Management: the International Journal for Industrial and High Tech Firms*, 49, 151-166. doi:10.1016/j.indmarman.2015.05.003
18. Nabila, S., & Nawawi, Z. M. (2025). Inovasi Penyusunan Elemen Pemasaran Organisasi Sebagai Upaya Penguatan Marketing Skill Praktis. *Jurnal Akademik Ekonomi dan Manajemen*, 2(2). doi:<https://doi.org/10.61722/jaem.v2i2.4779>
19. Noya, S., Taneo, S. Y., & Melany. (2025). The Impact of Export Market Orientation on SME Market Performance: Exploring the Moderating Effect of Government Policy and the Mediating Effect of Information Access. *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, 23(1), 146-157. doi:[http://dx.doi.org/10.21511/ppm.23\(1\).2025.11](http://dx.doi.org/10.21511/ppm.23(1).2025.11)
20. Nurhasanah, N., & Murwatiningasih, M. (2018). The Influence of Market Orientation, Learning Orientation, Innovation and Competitive Advantage to Improve Marketing Performance. *Management Analysis Journal*, 7(4). doi:10.15294/maj.v7i4.25637
21. Obadia, C., & Vida, I. (2024). Export Marketing Strategy and Performance: A Focus on SMEs Promotion. *International Business Review*, 33(2). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ibusrev.2023.102229>
22. Puke, I., Ulaga, W., & Enggers, F. (2022). Specific Marketing Capabilities for Improved Export Performance in Young Firms. *International Business Review*, 31(6). doi:10.54941/ahfe1002655
23. Rabbou, M. R., Adraoui, F. E., & Seddik, M. D. (2024). Evolution of Strategy Approaches in Management. *African Scientific Journal*, 3(27). doi:<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14288026>
24. Rayani, T. N., & Ibrahim, H. (2024). Tantangan Pengembangan Jaringan Pasokan Global Bagi Usaha Kecil, Mikro Dan Menengah (UMKM). *Jurnal Ilmu Manajemen, Ekonomi dan Kewirausahaan*, 2(2), 228. doi:<https://doi.org/10.58192/wawasan.v2i2.1826>
25. Ringo, J., Sabai, S., & Mahenge, A. (2024). Performance of Early Warning Systems in Mitigating Flood Effects. A Review. *Journal of African Earth Sciences*, 2(2). doi:10.1016/j.jafrearsci.2023.105134
26. Saragih, J. (2025). Driving Performance Through Innovation: The Roles of Communication and Competence in Public Sector Employees. *Khazanah Sosial*, 5(4), 734-749. doi:<https://doi.org/10.15575/ks.v5i4.19207>
27. Sari, I. H., Sinambela, K., & Hasibuan, R. U. (2025). Peran Perdagangan Internasional Terhadap Pertumbuhan Ekonomi Serta Peluang Dan Tantangan Yang Dihadapi Oleh Indonesia. *Jurnal Media Akademik*, 3(1), 2-7. doi:10.62281
28. Suhendri, Absah, Y., & Siahaan, E. (2023). Improving Company Competitive Advantage Through Transformational Leadership and the Pro-Growth Orgware quality. *International Journal of Management and Sustainability*, 12(4), 505-517. doi:10.18488/11.v12i4.3534
29. Syarafina, A. D., & Fitrianingrum, A. (2025). Pengaruh Innovation Capability, Export Marketing Strategy, Dan Export Market Orientation Terhadap Export Performance. *Jurnal Akuntansi, Manajemen dan Ilmu Ekonomi*, 5(2), 562-563. doi:[doi:10.54209/jasmien.v5i02.991](https://doi.org/10.54209/jasmien.v5i02.991)
30. Tambunan. (2019). Development of Small and Medium Enterprises in a Developing Country: The Indonesian Case. *Journal of Enterprising Communities*, 13(3), 301-317. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1108/JEC-06-2019-0053>
31. Teece, & David. (2007). Explicating Dynamic Capabilities: The Nature And Microfoundations Of Sustainable Enterprise Performance. *Strategic Management Journal*, 28(13), 1319-1350. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/smj.640>
32. Utomo, M. N., Pratiwi, S. R., & Windani, S. S. (2024). Kapabilitas Dinamis Sebagai Penentu Dalam Mengadopsi Penerapan Bisnis Berbasis Teknologi Digital. *Jurnal Nusantara Aplikasi Manajemen Bisnis*, 9(1), 20-32. doi:10.29407/nusamba.v9i1.18563